

Contamination Source Characterization in Water Distribution Network

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Contamination source identification in water distribution network has got serious attention during last two decades, especially in developed countries. The same effort is almost absent in developing countries. This paper introduces a contamination source identification methodology where EPANET is used for hydraulic and water quality simulation and genetic algorithm (GA) is used for the optimization. The methodology has been tested on two networks with increasing complexity. Sensitivity analysis on GA parameters shows the robustness of the methodology.

Keywords: Source identification, Genetic algorithm, Optimization, Sensitivity analysis.

Field of Research: Civil and Environmental Engineering, Water Resource Engineering, Water Quality Management, Water Network Security.

1. Introduction

Nowadays the quality of drinking water is of great concern worldwide. Drinking water quality may deteriorate in many ways, such as: water treatment deficiency, Leaching and corrosion, biofilm growth etc. Further, some external intrusion (accidental or intentional) of contaminants can also be possible. From the events of 9/11 2001 in US, people are becoming more serious about the security of water distribution systems (WDS), especially in US and Europe.

To ensure potable water, protective measures (increasing the security of water distribution line) should be taken so that the water not be affected by contaminants. Over the last two decades, the contamination source identification in WDS has got immense attention to the researchers. The research related to WDS's security has covered different aspects, the contamination source identification methodology (Laird et al. 2006, Di Cristo and Leopardi 2008, Preis and Ostfeld 2008, Huang and McBean 2009, Zechman and Ranjithan 2009, De Sanctis et al. 2010, Tryby et al. 2010), the optimal sensor displacement for an early warning (Ostfeld and Elad 2004, Ostfeld et al. 2004, Cozzolino et al. 2011, Edthofer et al. 2010), the detection of contamination events (Perelman et al. 2012, Olikier and Ostfeld 2014, Housh and Ostfeld 2015). Studies related to optimal sensor placement (Banik et al. 2016) and source identification (Banik et al. 2015) in wastewater network is also found in literature.

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Laird et al. (2006) proposed a two-phase mix integer quadratic programming approach where the main limitation is to find a unique solution. Di Cristo and Leopardi (2008) used the pollution matrix concept to identify the source location and concentration without focusing on exploring the starting time and duration of the contamination. A very similar procedure, as proposed in this paper, has been demonstrated by Preis and Ostfeld 2008, where genetic algorithm is used to optimize the source identification procedure. But they did not consider the location of sensors in the optimization outcome. De Sanctis et al. (2010) proposed a particle backtracking algorithm where the source concentration was not considered as a decision variable. Others (Huang and McBean 2009, Zechman and Ranjithan 2009) proposed some complex and time-consuming procedure which might be an issue for solving a large network.

In this paper, a simple and straightforward methodology to identify contamination source and its characteristics (concentration, starting time and duration) using Genetic Algorithm (GA) is presented. EPANET is used to perform the hydraulic and water quality simulation while GA is used to optimize the intrusion characteristics. Its effectiveness has been justified by applying the methodology on two different networks (Anytown USA, Network3) with increasing complexity. Moreover, a rigorous sensitivity analysis (GA parameters, sensor position, source location, pollution injection duration etc.) have also been performed which was not much emphasized previously on different research. Further, to the best of our knowledge, some sensor configurations not used in previous research are used here.

This paper is organized as: Section 2 deals with Methodology, Section 3 focuses on application and section 4 contains conclusion

2. Methodology

The methodology is based on linking EPANET with a GA which is a heuristic combinatorial search technique based on Darwin's evolution principle. It involves selection, crossover, and mutation. At first, initial population, consist of fixed number of individual solution, are generated by GA. After wards, it evaluates the fitness of each individual solution. And finally, based on the fitness score new population are generated through crossover and mutation.

Assumptions

Few assumptions have been made in order to accomplish the proposed methodology. Those are:

- A single continuous conservative pollutant is entering into a single node at a constant mass rate
- Monitoring stations are perfect and no uncertainty in sensor measurements and demand pattern is considered
- The flow through the pipe is considered as a Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR)

The steps of genetic algorithm have been shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Steps of a Genetic Algorithm (GA)

Four stages associated with the proposed methodology are described below.

Stage 1

The GA randomly generates a set of strings where each string consists of some decision variables, such as pollution source, concentration/mass rate of pollutant, starting time of injection, injection duration.

Pollution Source

A pollution source is randomly selected out of the entire set of nodes of the water distribution networks.

The Mass Rate of Pollutant

A random pollution mass rate has been chosen from a given range of mass rate. The pollution mass rate is considered being constant for the total injection duration. And the contaminant is injected in only one node at a time for the total injection duration.

Starting Time of Pollution Injection

Starting time is also generated randomly from a given range.

Injection Duration

Randomly chosen from a given range.

Stage 2

This stage computes the fitness value of each string by evaluating a fitness function. In the proposed methodology, the fitness or objective function is considered as the

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minimization of the absolute difference of the measured concentration at the monitoring stations and the simulated concentration values of the contaminant. Measured concentration values, which is eventually the sensor measurements, at different monitoring stations have been extracted through a synthetically produced contamination event in EPANET, while the simulated concentration is obtained by performing simulation using a GA produced string as input for EPANET. The objective function can be written as:

$$f = \sum_T^{T+t} |C_m - C_s|$$

Where, f is the fitness function value, T is the starting time of contaminant injected, t is the duration of contamination injection, C_m is the measured concentration at monitoring stations, C_s = simulated concentration at monitoring stations.

The monitoring stations are considered to be ideal and injected contaminants are considered having zero decay. All other EPANET parameters (i.e. demand patterns, plug flow, elevation of different nodes etc.) remain same as they are by default.

Stage 3

Based on the fitness score of each string, GA generates new set of population performing selection, mutation, and crossover. These new strings are better solutions than the previous generation and the solutions are expected to be improved in the successive generations.

Stage 4

The GA stops when a fixed number of maximum generation is attained. Finally, GA search the solution having minimum fitness score from the all simulations.

The proposed methodology has been demonstrated with a flow diagram in figure 2.

Figure 2: Demonstration of Proposed Methodology

3. Applications

The proposed methodology has been applied on two water distribution networks: Anytown USA, EPANET example-3. Further, different sensitivity analyses have been performed to check the robustness of the methodology.

Example 1: Anytown USA

The Anytown USA consists of 22 nodes including 2 tanks, 1 pump, and 1 reservoir. It has 38 pipes. The demand flow pattern, pipes, nodes, pumping station characteristics, tank are same as provided in Anytown USA by default. The layout of Anytown USA network has been shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Layout of Anytown USA

Three different optimal sensor configurations, having 3 sensors in a configuration, have been chosen from literature and tested for source identification methodology. At the same time, different arbitrary synthetic contamination events have been chosen to justify the methodology. The robustness of the methodology has also been checked by changing GA parameters (Population, Crossover probability and Mutation probability). Furthermore, the success of methodology has been checked for reduced number of decision variables. The analyses of three different cases are demonstrated below.

Case1: Sensitivity Analyses on Sensor Position

For this analysis, the GA parameters have been set as: population 100, generation 100, crossover probability 0.9 and mutation probability 0.01. The characteristics of the synthetic contamination event is chosen as: injection starting time 9 am, duration 2 hours and contaminant mass rate 15 g/min. These parameters will be named as **baserun** for next experiments of Example 1.

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Table1: Summary of the Sensitivity Analysis on Sensor Position (Example 1)

Sensor position	Injected node	Number of runs	Success rate in identifying correct node (%)	Detected mass rate (g/min)		No. of Successful detection of Starting time	No. of Successful detection of Duration
				Mean	Standard deviation		
8-12-19	3	20	80	14.69	1.56	16	16
	11	20	95	14.94	0.59	19	19
	17	20	85	15.03	.06	17	17
6-7-16	3	20	95	14.80	.42	19	19
	11	20	95	14.78	.45	19	19
	17	20	90	15.05	.092	19	19
7-16-19	3	20	85	14.99	.78	17	17
	11	20	95	14.8	.41	19	19
	17	20	90	15.02	.06	18	18

From Table 1, it can be seen that, regardless of sensor configuration or contamination source location the success rate in identifying the correct node is about 80% or above which is quite satisfactory. The detected concentration is also almost same as the synthetic event. Moreover, the success rate of detecting exact starting time and duration is also acceptable.

Case2: Sensitivity Analyses on GA Parameters

Among three different sensor dispositions stated above, only one configuration (8-12-19) and one source node (node 17) have been considered for analyzing the sensitivity of the GA parameters on the proposed methodology. When changing one parameter the other parameters are kept as the base run.

Table 2: Summary of Sensitivity Analysis on GA Parameters (Example 1)

GA parameter	Value of the parameter	Number of runs	Success rate in identifying correct node (%)	Detected mass rate (g/min)		No. of Successful detection of Starting time	No. of Successful detection of Duration
				Mean	Standard deviation		
Population	50	20	80	14.83	.64	16	16
	200	20	90	14.94	.28	18	18
Crossover	.85	20	90	14.99	.22	18	18
	.95	20	85	14.86	1.06	17	17
Mutation	0.1	20	95	15.14	.89	19	19
	0.05	20	90	15.06	.37	18	18

At the base run (in case-1) for the sensor position of 8-12-19 and the synthetic contamination source at node 17, the successful detection of source is 85 %. From table 2, it can be seen that changing population has a little impact on the outcomes. Success rate has decreased a little for less population. But as it is a small network the changes can be observed less clearly changing population as it will have less impact on a smaller network than a larger network. Mutation probability has an

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impact on the outcome. Changing it to 0.05 the success rate increases to 90% while changing it to 0.1 the success rate also increases to 95%. It is also observed that crossover probability has very little influence on the outcome.

Case 3: Considering Reduced Number of Decision Variable

The starting time and duration in GA variables are fixed here, only Nodes and Mass rate being the decision variables. This case has been analyzed for sensor configuration 8-12-19 and a synthetic contamination source at node 17, having all the other parameters same as the base value.

Table 3: Sensitivity on Reduced Number of Decision Variables (Example 1)

GA parameters	Number of runs	Successful detection of node	Success rate of source identification	Detected concentration (mean) g/min	Standard deviation g/min
Starting time and duration fixed	20	20	100%	15	0

From table 3, it can be seen that, fixing the starting time and duration of GA parameters (GA has only node position and mass rate as decision variable) have enough impact on the outcomes. It increases the success rate to 100%. The detected concentration is same as injected one (15g/min) with no standard deviation.

Example 2: EPANET Example 3

EPANET Example 3 consist of 92 nodes, two pumping stations, three storage tanks, a lake and a river. Demand flow pattern, pipe data etc. are same as in EPANET Example 3.

Two different configurations of sensors, having 5 sensors in a configuration, have been chosen initially and three different arbitrary synthetic contaminant source nodes have been selected for the analysis. Afterwards, different sensitivity analyses have been performed.

Case 1: Sensitivity Analyses on Sensor Position

For this analysis, the GA parameters were assigned as: population size of 100, generation of 100, crossover 0.9, mutation 0.1, pollution injection starting time 9 am, duration 2 hr. Contaminant mass rate 25 g/min. These parameters will be named as **base run** for next experiments of Example 2. The layout of EPANET example_3 network has been shown in figure 4.

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Figure 4: Layout of EPANET (Example 3)

Table 4: Summary of the Sensitivity Analysis on Sensor Position (Example 2)

Sensor position	Injected node	Number of runs	Success rate in identifying correct node (%)	Detected mass rate (g/min)		No. of Successful detection of Starting time	No. of Successful detection of Duration
				Mean	Standard deviation		
1-6-29-70-78	14	20	65	24.33	1.95	13	13
	36	20	50	24.2	2.95	10	10
	52	20	55	24.94	1.57	11	11
2-4-29-41-81	14	20	90	24.93	1.26	18	18
	36	20	65	24.73	2.14	13	13
	52	20	85	24.16	2.13	16	16

From table 4, it can be seen that for all the sensor positions and for different source nodes, the success rate is sensitive to sensor position and also source position. Of the two sensor configurations, the second one (2-4-29-41-81) seems to have better performance than the first one.

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Case 2: Sensitivity Analyses on GA Parameters

Of the two different sensor positions stated above, only one sensor position (1-6-29-70-78) and only one source node (node 52) have been chosen for further analysis to find out the influence of changing other parameters (GA) on the proposed methodology. When changing one parameter the other parameters are same as the base parameters stated above.

Table 5: Summary of Sensitivity Analysis on GA Parameters (Example 2)

GA parameters	Value of the parameters	Number of runs	Success rate in identifying correct node (%)	Detected mass rate (g/min)		No. of Successful detection of Starting time	No. of Successful detection of Duration
				Mean	Standard deviation		
<i>Population size</i>	50	20	60	25.53	1.91	12	12
	200	20	70	24.1	1.47	14	14
<i>Crossover</i>	.85	20	60	24.08	1.57	12	12
	.95	20	50	24.79	1.75	10	10
<i>Mutation</i>	0.01	20	40	24.7	.75	8	8
	0.2	20	60	24.3	1.23	12	12

At the base run (in case-1) for the sensor position of **1-6-29-70-78** and pollution source at node-**52**, the successful detection of source was 11 out of 20 runs. And success rate was 55 %.

From the table_5 it can be seen that changing the population has an impact on the outcomes. Population size of 50 has a success rate of 60% while population size of 200 has a success rate of 70%. So, increasing the population size seems to have a positive impact on the outcomes. On the other hand, changing mutation to 0.01 decrease the success rate to 40% while increasing the mutation to 0.2 increases the success rate to 60%. So, a larger mutation seems to have better performance for a larger network. Here also crossover don't seem to have enough impact on the performance of the methodology.

Case 3: Considering Reduced Number of Decision Variable

Fixing the starting time and duration in GA variables, only Nodes and Mass rate being the decision variables. For sensor position 1-6-29-70-78 and a pollution source at node 52, the case has been analyzed. Having all the parameters same as the base value.

Table 6: Sensitivity on Reduced Number of Decision Variables (Example 2)

GA parameters	Number of runs	Successful detection of node	Success rate of source identification	Detected concentration (mean) g/min	Standard deviation g/min
Starting time and duration fixed	20	20	100%	24.98	.04

From the above table 6, it can be seen that, fixing the starting time and duration in GA parameters (GA having only nodes and mass rate as variable) have enough impact on the outcomes. It increases the success rate to 100%. The detected concentration is also almost same as injected one (25 g/min) with only a little standard deviation of 0.04 g/min.

Case 4: Changing the Duration of Pollution Injection to 4 Hours

For sensor position 1-6-29-70-78 and a pollution source at node 52, the case has been analyzed. Having all the parameters same as the base value.

Table 7: Sensitivity Analysis of Changing Duration of Pollution Injection

GA parameters	Number of runs	Successful detection of node	Success rate of source identification	Detected concentration (mean) g/min	Standard deviation g/min
4 hr. of pollution injection at node 52.	20	11	55%	25.89	1.88

Increasing the pollution source injection time to 4hrs doesn't seem to have enough impact on the outcomes.

4. Conclusions

The proposed methodology is simple and easy to use, which can identify the characteristics (location, mass rate, starting time, duration) of a pollution source satisfactorily. Here the proposed methodology have been tested on two well-known water distribution networks along with three different sensitivity analyses (GA parameters, sensor position and source location) to find out the robustness of the methodology. It is observed that sensor configuration could be a vital factor in source identification in case of a large network. GA parameters are more or less sensitive in case of both networks. Pollution injection duration doesn't seem to have much impact on the detection rate. Reduction of the decision variables have a great impact on the results (100 % success rate using two decision variables, location and mass rate, instead of four decision variables for both networks). Further developments of the proposed methodology will be performed in the future works. The limitations of this research are:

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- Mass rate is considered to be constant, but in reality, that might not be the case.
- Pollution has been injected at only one node. Multiple pollution source hasn't been considered.
- Monitoring stations are considered to be perfect and no uncertainty in sensor measurements is considered.
- Demand pattern is considered to be known and no uncertainty is considered.

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